

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Optical Single Event Transients on SiPh components</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA13-439</i>
General application	<i>Space, high-energy accelerators</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Lauri Olantera, CERN</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Daniele Alfiero, CERN and University of Birmingham Stephane Detraz, CERN Carmelo Scarcella, CERN</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>23-24 September 2025</i>
Facility	<i>HIF, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>12 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The objective of this proposal was to investigate the susceptibility of silicon photonics (SiPh) components, specifically waveguides, to optical single event transients (OSETs) induced by heavy ions. OSETs arise when a single energetic particle generates dense electron–hole pairs in silicon, temporarily altering optical attenuation and refractive index and potentially degrading signal integrity. Although SiPh is a promising technology for data transmission in radiation-intense environments such as space missions and high-energy physics experiments, its response to single event effects remains largely unexplored. Previous studies have primarily focused on total ionizing dose and displacement damage, while simulations and laser-based tests suggest that individual energetic ions may cause transient disturbances. To our knowledge, this experiment is the first to study OSETs in silicon photonic waveguides using heavy-ion irradiation. The specific objective was to acquire transient measurements using ions with different linear energy transfer (LET) values and angles of incidence and to determine whether heavy-ion–induced OSETs constitute a genuine concern for silicon photonics–based data links.

Experiment test report

Test setup

The chosen test vehicle was the CERN-designed SystemPIC, a 5 × 5 mm photonic integrated circuit containing a wide variety of SiPh components, including waveguides, photodiodes, and ring modulators. Although the primary goal was to monitor and acquire transients from a single waveguide structure (length = 7.5 mm, width = 380 nm) on one chip, a total of five chips were mounted on the test board and all were exposed to the same ion flux for the full duration of the test. This approach provided additional statistics for observing potential permanent damage caused by heavy-ion irradiation. Only

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/radnext>

the main chip under test was optically coupled, using a 24-channel fiber array unit and on-chip grating couplers.

A battery-powered distributed feedback (DFB) laser operating at a wavelength of 1310 nm, thermally stabilized by an ILX laser diode controller, provided constant optical power. A battery pack was used to minimize noise in the laser bias current supply and thereby improve output power stability. This configuration allowed triggering close to the baseline and enabled the capture of transients as small as 1% of the full signal amplitude while reducing false triggers.

A manual polarization controller was used to optimize the polarization state before coupling the signal into the waveguide under test via on-chip grating couplers. The optical output from the chip was converted into an electrical signal using a reference receiver with a 9.3 GHz bandwidth (Agilent 81495A) and then DC-coupled to a 6 GHz mixed-signal oscilloscope (Keysight MXR254A). DC coupling was employed to remove the signal offset and improve sensitivity to small transient signals, with amplitude information provided by the reference receiver.

No additional control signals or settings were used: the sample consisted solely of passive waveguide structures, making the experimental setup and measurement procedure straightforward. The test was started with a run using the highest LET ion available in the HIF 9.3 MeV/n cocktail (Xe, 61.3 MeV/(mg/cm²)) and with a 0° angle of incidence, followed by runs with Rh (45.0 MeV/(mg/cm²)) and Kr (31.7 MeV/(mg/cm²)) and 45° and 75° angles of incidence. All runs used the highest ion flux available 15000 ions/(s×cm²).

Results

The largest observed transient obtained with Xe ions at a 0° angle of incidence is shown in Figure 1. This transient was captured during a 15-minute run using a 1% trigger level. The stability of the input optical power proved to be challenging despite our mitigation efforts. Although the achieved stability of better than ±1% is excellent for the used light-source configuration, low-frequency power drift was present and propagated through the DC coupling into the oscilloscope. As a result, the baseline level drifted within around ±0.5%, and because the 1% trigger threshold did not track this fluctuation, some transients with amplitudes near 1% were not recorded. In total only 14 transients were captured during the 15-minute run.

If we conservatively estimate that approximately half of the transients were detected, this implies that only about 10% of the ions striking the waveguide area produced a transient of sufficient amplitude. This indicates that only ion hits occurring near the center of the waveguide, where the optical mode intensity is highest and the overlap between ion-induced charge carriers and the optical mode is greatest, can generate detectable attenuation transients. Subsequent measurements using lower-LET ions at a 0° angle of incidence did not yield any measurable transients. These initial results already suggest that high LET ions are required to generate enough carriers to produce any meaningful optical attenuation, and even under these conditions, the transient amplitudes are insufficient to significantly degrade data transmission.

Figure 1. Largest transient measured using Xe ions and 0-degree angle of incidence.

Increasing the angle of incidence increases the ion path length through the waveguide, leading to a larger volume of generated charge carriers and greater overlap with the optical mode. This is expected to increase the transient amplitudes, which was indeed clearly observed in the measured transient amplitudes. The 45° angle increases the maximum path length around 50% while 75° increases the maximum path length almost 400%. However, as the waveguide on the chip is L-shaped rotating the sample beyond 45° increases the path length significantly in only about half of the waveguide length. Therefore, with the 75° angle of incidence two distinct distributions appear, Figure 2. Even at the largest angle the maximum transient amplitude remained below 4% with the highest LET Xe ions, and below 2% with Kr ions, Figure 2.

Figure 2. Transient amplitudes measured using 75-degree angle of incidence and Xe and Kr ions.

Testing of all irradiated chips for potential permanent damage is still pending as an automated test setup is being developed.

Conclusions

The *Optical Single Event Transients on SiPh components* heavy-ion test campaign, conducted within the RADNEXT project, was successful and produced a good dataset that demonstrates the effects of heavy ions on waveguides. The test setup was sufficiently sensitive to capture weak transients and provided enough resolution to distinguish between different LET ions and angles of incidence. A positive outcome was the observation that transient amplitudes were not large enough to cause any significant degradation in SiPh-based data links. Only ions with LETs higher than 30 MeV/(mg/cm²) produced measurable transients. This indicates that in an LHC-like environment, where the largest LETs are due to silicon recoils with values around 15 MeV/(mg/cm²), OSETs are not expected to pose a concern. This conclusion can also be extended to space applications, where high-LET ions exist but are so rare that even observable events would occur at a “once-per-year” frequency.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.